

Languages, culture, and translation in modern linguistics: comparative approaches
INNOVATIVE CLASSROOM TECHNIQUES IN TEACHING READING FOR YOUNG LEARNERS

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***Annotation.** This article discusses how to teach young learners to read using creative classroom tactics and procedures. Students can improve their reading cohesion and coherence skills by strengthening grammar, expanding their vocabulary, practicing with peers, and utilizing modern teaching tools. Reading and comprehending it are both tough and interesting experiences for students. Hence, they will grow significantly at each stage of their education.*

***Key words.** Innovative, classroom, method, technique, reading, young learners, teaching.*

Introduction. “A reader lives a thousand lives before he dies. The man who never reads lives only one.” – George R.R. Martin[1]. In these days making students read and comprehend one book or text is the most difficult teaching way for teachers. Teaching young students to read is an important part of their educational journey. Traditional tactics are effective, but they fall short in captivating today's tech-savvy and dynamic young brains. Innovative classroom practices have evolved as a transformative strategy, combining creativity, technology, and interactive strategies to improve reading engagement and effectiveness. Integrating these current strategies allows educators to not only improve kids' literacy skills but also promote a lifetime love of reading.

Literature

Some essential elements need to be developed in teaching English as a foreign language for children. One of them is developing reading skills as an effective medium for teachers in introducing vocabulary for children. In reading, the practice involves some important processes, including mechanical eye movement,

intellectual comprehension, such as imagining, reasoning, evaluating, and problem solving, grammar, and phonetics (Wibowo et al., 2020). These might create a distinctive challenge for children to go with the process [2].

Reading can be powerful skill, but it is important to approach it with the right mindset and techniques. One of the best reading techniques that you can choose for your students is the ability for them to have a choice in what they read. This is the most effective to get your students to want to read. By setting clear reading goals, engaging in active reading, and choosing the right books, you can get the most out of any book you read[3].

Comprehending and doing innovative activities are not the main purpose of teaching reading. First of all, teachers need to explain how to set goals and select appropriate books or texts while learning a new language. When students select reading materials, they should consider their reading purposes and interests. One of the common ways of selecting and determining aims is to write interests and requirements what kind of materials they need.

Methods

Balance activities

Reading is one of the difficult sections in learning language. Young learners might be bored with doing long-lasting activities and games even if they are interesting. As Dr. Richards told: “Activities of five to ten minutes in length are most successful. A balance between the following kinds of activities is often useful”[4]. Therefore, teachers should prepare unique, short and effective materials for students to learn reading in a right way.

Gamified reading

In the classroom just reading and discussing it are traditional ways. Teachers can organize innovative games such as Kahoot! , Quizizz or Blooket where students answer comprehension questions after reading. Tests should be creative and interactive. Also, teacher can add an element of competition and fun to motivate learners.

Augmented reality (AR)

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In this method, students learn through technology. This will make reading more interactive and stimulating curiosity. There are some apps like Quiver or merge Cube to bring stories to life. For example, while reading a book about animals, students can scan images to see 3D animations of those animals. Students read not only texts or books, but also visualize pictures what they read.

Material we use in reading skills. They are following (table 1).

Short stories
Plays
Letters, postcards, notes
Newspapers, magazines, TV guides
Advertisements
Puzzles, problems, rules for games
Instructions, directions, rules, regulations, posters, notices, road signs, price list, menu etc.

Results and discussion

Students need to know how to use technologies appropriately in learning new things. They can improve their language skills and correct their errors with the help of modern technologies. The study also explored various innovative techniques for teaching reading to young learners and how they contribute to improving literacy skills. The findings indicate that integrating creative, interactive, and technological methods can significantly enhance students' engagement and comprehension.

The innovative approaches help learners more than the traditional ones that they lose interest not only reading, but also whole subject. By combining technologies with active participation, students can overcome the challenges of doing reading activities during the lesson. However, successful teaching techniques require being planned carefully by the teachers. The teachers need adequate training to use methods such as gamified platforms and AR tools. Additionally, maintaining a balance between traditional and innovative methods is important to avoid focusing technology overly.

Some of the sub skills that we can be used in Reading practice lessons:

Predicting, skimming, scanning, questioning, modeling, blank, filling, sequencing, sensitizing, matching, summarizing, Dictionary skills, silent reading.

Conclusion. This article explores innovative classroom strategies and practices for teaching young language learners to read. By using contemporary instructional resources, practicing with peers, increasing vocabulary, and improving grammar, students can increase their reading cohesion and coherence. Students find reading and understanding it to be both challenging and engaging. As a result, kids will develop considerably throughout their schooling.

USED OF LITERATURES

1. George R.R. Martin, “A dance with Dragons” is a book published Bantam Books on July 12, 2011, p-452.
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3. Effective techniques in teaching reading for young learners <https://doi.org/10.47689/XXIA-TTIPR-vol1-iss1-pp369-370>.
4. Jack C. Richards, Methods and techniques for young learners, [Methods and Techniques for Young Learners - Professor Jack C. Richards](#)